

Enhancing Information Access in Nigerian University Libraries in the ChatGPT Era: Strategic Approaches and Key Considerations

Ibrahim M. M. Furfuri, Ph.D

Inuwa Abdul-Kadir Library, Sokoto State University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

immfurfuri@yahoo.co.uk & ibrahim.furfuri@ssu.edu.ng

Abstract

This paper explored strategic approaches and key considerations on how university libraries in Nigeria can adopt chatGPT to enhance information access for efficiency of operations and service delivery. Systematic analysis and review of literature approaches were employed to determine the present state of the adoption of artificial intelligence in libraries. Specifically, the literature reveal that there is higher rate of AI adoption in academic libraries in America and European countries while it is slow in Asia and Oceania. But, the situation of the academic libraries in Africa indicate lack of readiness for the adoption of AI tools for offering library services. Hence, some strategies and key considerations were discussed briefly in order to guide the implementation of chatGPT. These strategies include the use of chatGPT to: enhance accuracy of cataloguing and its searching, enhance reference and information services, tailoring library resources for offering personalized services based on user's profiles and information seeking behaviour, providing training of library staff and patrons, gathering feedbacks from patrons for the purpose of decision making and service improvement. Therefore, the practical steps to be developed including policy framework to regulate the use of chatGPT were recommended. Furthermore, the paper discussed possible challenges and necessary precautions to be addressed for effective implementation and utilization of chatGPT to enhance information access in Nigerian university libraries.

Keywords: Information Access, Artificial Intelligence, ChatGPT Adoption, Nigerian University Libraries.

Introduction

Information access in the artificial intelligence (AI) era involves leveraging emerging technologies to utilize the appropriate tools to support searching and utilization of information resources from variety of sources. According to Faga and Yusuf (2023) the benefits to be derived by the adoption of AI in libraries include improvement of operational efficiency, library engagement of large number of patrons through enhance user experience and new services. For university libraries in developing countries, including Nigeria, to remain impactful to academic communities, librarians have to take advantage of AI tools such as chatGPT in order to enhance information access for effective housekeeping operations and service provision. By focusing on adoption of chatGPT in the university libraries, information access could be enhanced to satisfy the specific needs, demands and preferences of students and faculty members. ChatGPT is one of the AI tools that is trending to ease information access, particularly in education and research activities. ChatGPT has the potentials to bring positive changes in libraries in terms of enhancing productivity of staff and increase in users' satisfaction by promoting easy access to information sources and resources.

Generally, AI tools are increasingly recognized as indispensable in achieving seamless housekeeping operations and users satisfaction in libraries. However, studies reveal that, the application of the AI tools in Nigerian libraries is still at its infancy stage (Ogwo, Ibegbulem & Nwachukwu, 2023). Moreover, in the present period of information explosion, libraries in Nigeria are facing challenges of information access, and the situation is affecting the overall efficiency of their operations and service delivery (Effiong & Aagboke, 2022). This implied that, information access tools have influence on accessibility and utilization of information resources in present day libraries. Therefore, the availability of mass quantity of information is increasing rapidly due to excessive, uncontrollable and addicted use of internet resources. According Mole (2023), the digital age had resulted into tremendous and overwhelming information and information sources. Hence, one of the major roles of university libraries in facilitating information access has become a daunting task. Thus, an understanding of strategic approach and key considerations regarding chatGPT will bring positive change towards enhancing information access in university libraries (Hussaini, 2023). Focusing on fundamental strategies and considerations for the adoption and implementation of chatGPT is necessary because it will further motivate librarians towards engaging library users to access the needed resources and services efficiently and effectively. In other words, this AI tool can facilitate university library operations to progress in the right direction that could meet users' information access patterns, preferences, and expectations.

In fact, AI is an area of computer science that is concerned with creating intelligent machines that works and respond to information in the same manner as human beings (Mehan, 2022). The American Association of School Administrators (2023) had also describes AI as part of computer science discipline, designed with human cognitive abilities, and it is capable of handling tasks as done by human intelligence. According to this Association, based on the functions they perform, AI tools are in three categories, namely: Reactive, Predictive, and Generative tools. Reactive tools are part of AI technologies that react to inputs without making reference to previous experiences. The predictive tools on the other hand, are designed to analyze data base on history and experiences for prediction of future outcomes. However, the Generative AI was designed purposely to generate new outputs from mass datasets. ChatGPT is a model under the Generative AI category. Since the emergence of Open AI in June 2018, popularly known as ChatGPT-1, it has been upgraded through different phases up to ChatGPT-5 (Hussain, 2024). Today, it has become a powerful tool that understand and generate human-like text.

The chatGPT is a powerful AI conversational tool that can perform basic functions of adding value to library operations and services, most especially enhancement of information access. This implied that, the traditional information access tools such as card catalogue and bibliographies can no longer serve as basic means to enhance access to information in libraries. The application of ChatGPT in university libraries has the potentials to bring innovations that could meet users' rapidly changing information seeking behaviours. Therefore, it is necessary that, university libraries focus attention on different strategic approaches and key considerations for effective user engagements. Indeed, the university faculty members, students and researchers, require access to quality information resources with all precisions and timeliness. However, the university libraries in Nigeria like their counterparts in other developing countries are operating under challenging information environment. Some of these challenges as reported in literatures include rapidly changing users' information seeking behaviour and information needs, continuous increase in

students' enrolments, rapid evolving technologies, competitions from information service providers other than the libraries, and inadequate budgets allocations (Ogbonnaya, 2021).

In the present chatGPT era, it is necessary for the university libraries in Nigeria to redefine their roles and functions to be in line with global best practices. This will enable the libraries to operate and progress with the needs and aspirations of the academic communities they are meant to serve. In other words, the present situation of information overload and users' preferences make it imperative for university libraries to harness chatGPT potentials in order to remain responsive to information needs of their customers, and to cater for their diverse needs. A study by Emumejakpor, Ovie and Ekuerhare (2024), on AI adoptions in Nigerian libraries, indicated strong need to increase field study for effective deployment of the technology for offering library services. This paper therefore, aimed at exploring the strategic approaches and key considerations on how university libraries in Nigeria can adopt and implement ChatGPT to enhance information access for efficiency of operations and service delivery.

Information Access Tools

Due to advances in technology, it is necessary for university libraries to integrate both conventional and AI based information access provision as part of the basic requirements for efficient and effective service delivery. Information access provision in this context is concerned with getting contents of the information resources into the library for effective operations and service delivery to users (Mole, 2023). On the other hand, information access tools are information location tools that assist in identification of accessible information sources in a library (Udofot & Nwachukwu, 2022). However, in Nigerian universities, despite the indispensable role of digital technologies, the conventional and AI based information access tools are key to accessing information to facilitate library operations and service delivery. The role of information access tools is to facilitate access to information sources and its use (Effiong & Aagboke, 2022). This implied that, without efficiency of the information access tools, the information resources of a university library will be underutilized, and consequently render the library less important to its target users.

In fact, in Nigeria, the traditional information access tools have not been abolished completely but their usage is fast declining. These traditional tools as stated by Nwachukwu and Ogwo (2014) include major ones such as bibliographies, abstracts, catalogues, indexes, and directories. But, in the electronic information environment, the popular information access tools that are in use include online public access catalogue (OPAC), online databases, institutional repositories, CD-ROMs, internet search engines, subjects' gateways, elibrary portals, web directories, and so on. This means presently, libraries provide users with variety of information access tools, which are in traditional and digital formats. These access tools aid both librarians and users to identify and locate information sources available within a university library or from other remote locations linked to the library. Thus, the adoption of chatGPT, require university libraries to employ appropriate strategies to facilitate information discovery and retrieval for enhancement of its operations and services.

A study by Udoh, Okafor and Ekpenyong (2020) at Micheal Opara University of Agriculture, Umudike, South-East Nigeria revealed that, in addition to conventional library catalogues, bibliographies, abstracts and indexes, other strategic information access tools in electronic formats

are indispensable for accuracy and speedy information access. These researchers noted that, information access has not been achieved fully due to inadequate trained library staff to handle digital information access tools such as OPAC, MARC 21, and Dublin Core. However, the emergence of chatGPT can enhance information access if appropriate strategies and considerations are put in place. Therefore, access provision to enable librarians get contents of information resources to satisfy the needs of their customers can be done seamlessly by the adoption and strategic implementation of AI tools such as ChatGPT. Strategic Approaches for Using ChatGPT to Enhance Information Access in University Libraries

The implementation of chatGPT offer several benefits in information access for both librarians and users in Nigerian university libraries. In this context of this paper, strategic approach refers to plan of actions developed to serve as guide towards effective adoption and successful implementation of chatGPT as an AI tool to achieve specific goals objectives of enhancing information access. Below are specific examples on strategic approaches for the adoption and implementation of chatGPT to enhance information access:

ChatGPT can greatly enhance the process of cataloguing and search the library catalogue. This means both library staff and users can leverage chatGPT to search and locate books, journal articles and other information resources within the university library catalogues and even beyond. Based on natural language processing, chatGPT can decode inquiries and provide librarians with results that is appropriate to a search done. By using this tool, it can extract relevant information that will improve the quality and speed of organizing data to achieve accurate cataloguing and metadata management (Shehu & Dikko, 2024).

According to Prathibha and Shilpa, (2021) the use of chatGPT can provide answers to common reference questions about library resources, services and policies. The delivery of this form of reference service will enhance access to information in a speedy and efficient manner. Therefore, if it is well implemented, the job of library staff will be reduced, and this may give them opportunities to attend to other aspects of library work. A study by Hussain (2024) provide practical guidelines on how practicing librarians can implement chatGPT for academic purposes including reference services. Thus, chatGPT can offer guidance to enable librarians make quick discovery and retrieval of information resources for answering reference questions and to also serve as virtual reference librarian. This implied that, if deployed properly, chatGPT can help librarians to overcome excess workload, especially in handling complex queries from the library patrons.

Personalization refers to the process of tailoring an experience of an individual library user based on his personal data or profile that is related to unique reading or search preferences, specific interests, or information seeking behavior. University libraries can also leverage chatGPT to tailor their collections and services to meet patrons needs in a more effective and efficient manner. For instance, chatGPT can analyze data on how patrons use information resources and their history of search queries. Consequently, this data will enable libraries plan and offer personalized and customized resources and services (Shehu & Dikko, 2024). In addition, ChatGPT can be used to analyzed this data and create an in depth and more engaging connection with the library user (Soylu, 2023). Therefore, based on this personalized approach, chatGPT can enhance information

access in different ways. Some of these personalized information access as pointed out by Mali and Deshmukh (2023) are as follows:

(a) recommending books for readers. This is very helpful especially for readers without any book or author in mind.

(b) language translation and learning. ChatGPT can be integrated with language translation software and enable a library user to communicate in a specifically chosen language. In addition, language learning materials can be accessed for a user to practice both speaking and writing of that language. Thus, bi/multilingual support for inclusive access to library resources and services can be achieved.

(c) chatGPT can offer access to vast array of information resources. Resources such as books, journal articles and other related materials can be made more accessible through the use of chatGPT by way of audio description of visual contents or transcriptions of video contents. Thus, the interests of various user groups in a library can be satisfied including users with special needs.

Through the use of chatGPT, library information resources collection can be updated regularly to reflect new information from research findings and other trending topics in different disciplines. AI tools such as chatGPT can be regarded as a cost effective open access technology that can be explored to enhance library operations and services by bringing positive innovations and research support to patrons. In other words, despite its limitations this technology can enhance access to relevant databases and topics that can empower librarians to assist researchers. Hence, chatGPT will enable libraries and librarians to offer a more effective research support by providing guide to more complex research questions.

In this approach, since AI is data-driven, librarians can use chatGPT to collect feedback from patrons in order to evaluate and determine their level of satisfaction with services for the purpose of decision making and improvement. Furthermore, the data gathered from users' queries and information use patterns can be useful in making needs analysis for collection development process.

University libraries can use chatGPT to obtain information for identifying areas of training needs, especially on new innovations that are very essential for global best practices in library operations and service delivery. ChatGPT can also be used to provide training to library users and offer support that will help them towards better understanding and utilization of the tool. This training is necessary because the complexity of present day information environment require strategic approach and consideration of various methodologies and challenges of implementation (Gaur, 2025).

The use of chatGPT to enhance information access are many including interactive tutorials, collaboration opportunities, and identification of quality information resources that are on top demands by researchers. Fig 1 below illustrated the ways to use chatGPT; step-by-step.

The Ways to Use ChatGPT (SOURCE: College Vidya, 2023, Dec. 11).

Key Considerations for Using ChatGPT in Nigerian University Libraries

The use of chatGPT in the academia, particularly in the university is raising serious concerns in terms of quality education, academic integrity and honesty, and different issues pertaining to research ethics. However, the use of chatGPT may still remain skeptical, especially on the part of faculty members in terms of academic integrity, dishonesty and plagiarism issues. But, for the libraries, this tool is a welcome development because of its potentials towards facilitating efficiency of operations and productivity, and enhancement user experience (Affum, 2023). Furthermore, Cox and Tzoc (2023), noted that, the emergence of chatGPT was so amazing because it had reached over a million users within a week of its launching in late November, 2022. These researchers stated that “ChatGPT is a large language model (LLM) that serve as a tool that uses deep learning techniques to generate text in response to questions posed to it. It can also generate essays, email, song lyrics, recipes, computer code, webpages, even games and medical diagnoses”. Thus, instead of searching the internet, ChatGPT has been trained to handle large collection of textual contents, such as news and academic articles, books, websites, and many other sources of information. It also has data from multiple languages and computer codes. Hence, the generation of texts by chatGPT is accomplished by predicting the next word in a series of words so that it can produce sentences and then entire pages of contents (Cox & Tzoc, 2023). This implied that, adoption and implementation of chatGPT in university libraries will optimized information access services like OPAC, reference service, bibliographic service, and customer relations.

According to Bin-Nashwan, Sadallah and Bouteraa (2023) chatGPT has gained wider acceptability in the academics because of the profound benefits it offers in terms academic contents it generate and made accessible. However, these scholars further maintain that, use of chatGPT raised “concerns about academic honesty and plagiarism, which is facilitating the violation of ethical principles of the academic system. But, in this paper, chatGPT is considered as another advanced innovation for enhancing access to information. It is just a tool to help librarians to access information thereby reducing their workload and improve service delivery. This means, people can use this tool for good or evil depending on the approach of the user and the output he wants to

achieve. So regardless of the disadvantages or criticisms, and whether it is accept or not, chatGPT as a tool has come to stay in the academics. Based on its potential benefits, particularly in enhancing information access, it is imperative that university libraries in Nigeria develop and adopt some key considerations that are very vital for ethical use of chatGPT. Below are some key considerations to be made for proper adoption and implementation of chatGPT in the university libraries:

I. Practical steps to be considered for the successful adoption of chatGPT: University libraries should consider the ethical concerns of using chatGPT and come up with acceptable level of using such technology (Danquah, Dadzie, Gyesi & Yeboah, 2024). Thus, adequate training to build competence of library staff in adoption of AI is indispensable. For proper deployment of AI tools including chatGPT, Guar (2025) recommended some practical steps to be considered for the successful adoption. These steps are highlighted as follows:

- 1) Definition of clear objectives that focused on problems to be solved such as enhancing information access by libraries
- 2) Ensure comprehensive data preparation process
- 3) Choosing the appropriate AI tool to be deployed
- 4) Ensure building skilled AI team
- 5) Implement the AI project in phases and pilot test it
- 6) Ensure monitoring and evaluation of the project for its successful outcomes and sustainability

The university libraries should explore the possible benefits and challenges as it relates to their academic environment, and then map out the appropriate strategies to guide the implementation of this tool. By doing this, chatGPT will be adapted in a responsible and ethical manner, to effectively enhance information access for facilitating research and scholarly activities.

II. Policy framework for regulating the use of chatGPT: University libraries should have institutional policy to regulate the ethical use of chatGPT and other AIs. In this regard, it is necessary to create awareness, sensitized and educate user community for proper use of this tool. Thus, local software developers within the institution should be given support towards customization of chatGPT to be in line with users' needs and the Nigerian education system in general. For instance, Bin-Nashwan, Sadallah and Bouteraa (2023) argued that, academic integrity hangs in the balance because of the emergence and usage of chatGPT in research, publications and other scholarly outputs. These researchers recommended that stakeholders and most especially AI language models programmers should work together and come up with necessary guidelines for ethical use of AI tools such as chatbots and chatGPT. Danquah, Dadzie, Gyesi & Yeboah (2024) suggests key strategies for the implementation of AI including chatGPT in academic libraries in Ghana. These strategies include development of relevant policy and plan, training and educating library staff and their patrons on AI applications for library use, guidelines on the AI ethical use, and its inclusion in library and information science curriculum.

II. Identification of training needs of librarians and other stakeholders: It is very important that librarians and their user community and other stakeholders are properly trained towards positive usage of chatGPT. Factors that could motivate the use of chatGPT by library users should be brought to limelight with a view to shape their behaviour towards ethical usage. This means

researchers or scholars that are conscious of their academic integrity may not bother much about the use chatGPT for their academic works. Hence, if people are well trained they will have self-direction for enhanced information access.

III. Librarians to engage in lifelong learning: This means professional librarians should actively engaged in continuous learning to enable them keep up-to-date in their professional practices. Thus, interactions with their customers will always earn them recognition and respect because they are perceived as partners in teaching, learning and research. It is through lifelong learning that librarians can add value to their professional job, and at the same time train and expose their customers to become effective information consumers in a responsible way. In the present digital world, without continuous learning, librarians will not have the required skill sets and confidence to interact with library users.

IV. Precaution to library users: It is very crucial that library users are given the necessary precautions about the use of chatGPT. The precautions should aim at educating the users about the Dos and Don'ts while using chatGPT. Aithal and Aithal (2023) suggests that library users should be cautious to use cahtGPT as a supplement to conventional approach in accessing information. Different sources of information should also be use to verify the accuracy of information accessed through chatGPT. Other areas of precaution include biasness and lack of reliability of information on certain topics, dynamic nature of AI technologies, the need for teamwork and collaborations in using the technology, privacy, confidentiality and security of individual user's data or personal profile, etc.

V. Cost of implementation: This is another area of major consideration. In other words, conceptualization, planning, implementation and sustainability considerations are very vital for successful adaption and use of chatGPT technology in university libraries. Therefore, SWOT analysis is very fundamental in determining the positive and negative sides of the adaption of chatGPT.

Possible Challenges of Using ChatGPT in Nigerian University Libraries

Despite its crucial role towards enhancing information access, the use of chatGPT in Nigerian university libraries can be more challenging than other technologies deployed in the past, which many librarians are still grappling with unimpressive success stories. Specifically, in adoption and use of AI tools libraries in African are still lagging behind. For instance, Danquah, Dadzie, Gyesei & Yeboah (2024) conducted a scoping literature review of 478 articles on AI in libraries published from October 2022 to November 2023 in Scopus database. The overall focus of the published articles were in three perspectives: firstly awareness, readiness, and understanding of what AI can do in libraries, secondly AI tools relevant for academic library service provision, and thirdly attitudes, acceptance, and perceptions of librarians towards AI implementation including challenges and future directions. Furthermore, the findings indicate higher rate of the AI adoption in academic libraries in America and European countries while slow in Asia and Oceana. However, the study further reveal that, the academic libraries in Africa seems not ready for the adoption of AI in offering library services. This suggest the need for university libraries in Nigeria to act swiftly to overcome their peculiar challenges concerning AI adoptions.

In this regard, the possible challenges associated using chatGPT in Nigerian university libraries include inefficiency of internet connectivity and related infrastructure, poor funding, skills gaps among librarians, ineffective institutional policy, and lack of stable power source (Azubuike & Uzomba, 2021). The limitations of chatGPT is one of its major challenge to be address by librarians. These limitations include unreliable or lack of accurate information in some instances. Other possible limitations as pointed out in relevant literature include initial cost implications, issues of protection of user privacy, low AI literacy among librarians, biasness in AI algorithms, and attitudes of librarians regarding losing jobs, irregular power supply, resistance to change, poor maintenance culture, lack of required skill sets and technical expertise (Akinyemi, 2023; Ogwo, Ibegbulem & Nwachukwu, 2023). Despite these challenges, librarians should develop positive attitude and willingness to embrace creativity, innovations and change for proper integration of chatGPT for enhancing information access (Balasubramanian & Tamilelvan, 2023). However, with proper planning to ensure positive perception of library staff, adequate funding for the project, and necessary training, the possible challenges can be addressed or mitigated.

Conclusion

The use of chatGPT to enhanced information access in university libraries cannot be overemphasized. This paper provide some insights on potential benefits of AI adoption in academic libraries for enhancement of information access. Specifically, AI tools such as chatGPT can greatly enhance information access if appropriate strategies are developed and implemented. Therefore, some strategic approaches and key considerations were highlighted for effective implementation of chatGPT in Nigerian university libraries. However, the systematic analysis and review of literature reveal that while libraries in the developed counties are progressing in terms of AI adoption and implementation, the situation of academic libraries in Africa is not encouraging. Hence, in order to enhance information access, the heads of Nigerian university libraries are required to be more proactive towards developing strategies and making key considerations for the adoption and implementation of AI tools like chatGPT. The specific areas that chatGPT can be used to improve operational efficiency for information access in university libraries were brought to limelight in this paper. These areas include cataloguing, information searching, reference and information services, recommendation of books for collection development, reading, and research support. The key considerations for the implementation of chatGPT include developing practical steps and policy framework to guide and regulate the use of chatGPT. The possible challenges such as limitations of chatGPT in terms of biasness, inaccuracy of information in some instances were pointed out. Other challenges to be addressed include low funding of libraries, and gaps in required skill-sets of librarians.

References

- Affum, M. Q. (2023). The role of artificial intelligence in library automation. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), Article 7880. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7880>
- Aithal, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2023). Effects of AI-based ChatGPT on higher education libraries. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 8(2), 95–108. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7905052>
- Akinyemi, O. (2023). Enhancing academic library service delivery using artificial intelligence (AI). *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), Article 8042. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/8042>

- American Association of School Administrators. (2023). Bringing AI to school: Tips for school leaders. <https://www.aasa.org/resources/resource/bringing-ai-to-school-tips-for-school-leaders>
- Azubuikwe, F. C., & Uzomba, C. E. (2021). Smart technology and artificial intelligence in libraries: A synergy for library service optimization. *Global Review of Library and Information Science (GRELIS)*, 17(2), 1–12
- Balasubramanian, S., & Tamilselvan, N. (2023). Exploring the potential of artificial intelligence in library services: A systematic review. *International Journal of Library and Information Science (IJLIS)*, 12(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/S9RWDBin->
- Nashwan, S. A., Sadallah, M., & Boutera, M. (2023). Use of ChatGPT in academia: Academic integrity hangs in the balance. *Technology in Society*, 75, Article 102370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2023.102370>
- Vidya. (2023, December 11). What is ChatGPT? 10 ways to use ChatGPT for students. <https://collegevidya.com/blog/how-to-use-chat-gpt-for-students/>
- Cox, C., & Tzoc, E. (2023). ChatGPT: Implications for academic libraries. *College & Research Libraries News*, 84(3), 98–99. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.84.3.99>
- Danquah, M. M., Dadzie, P. S., Gyesei, K., & Yeboah, F. (2024). Artificial intelligence implementation strategies for Ghanaian academic libraries: A scoping review. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2024.102975>
- Effiong, A. E., & Aagboke, A. L. (2022). Information access tools and utilization of information resources by medical students in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, Article 7192. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7192>
- Emumekpor, E. O., Ovie, E. C., & Ekuerhare, O. (2024). Adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) in library services for national development: A review of literature. *Niger Delta Journal of Library and Information Science*, 5(1). <https://ndjlis.fuotuo.ke.edu.ng>
- Ezekwe, B., & Muokebe, B. (2012). Access tools as information retrieval tools. In *Information literacy, sustainable development goals and library and information education (Proceedings of the 20th National Conference of the Nigeria Association of Educators, September 17–21, 2018, Benue State University, Makurdi)*.
- Faga, A., & Yusuf, A. O. (2023). Adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) in library parlance: Issues and benefits. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, Article 7691. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7691>
- Hussain, A. (2023). Use of artificial intelligence in library services: Prospects and challenges. *Library Hi Tech News*, 40(2), 15–17. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHTN-11-2022-0125>
- Hussain, A. (2024). Unlocking the potentials of ChatGPT in academic libraries. *IP India Journal of Library Science and Information Technology*, 9(2), 80–89. <https://www.ijlsit.org/>
- Kaur, B. (2025). The impact of artificial intelligence on academic library functions leveraging competency frameworks and professional theory. In R. N. Malviya, S. Chand, B. K. Mishra, A. A. Jha, & M. K. Dwivedi (Eds.), *Innovative library practices in the digital era: Aligning with National Education Policy for Viksit Bharat 2047* (pp. 640–656). Discount Group of Publication.
- Mali, T. S., & Deshmukh, R. K. (2023). Use of ChatGPT in library services. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, f264–f266.

- Mehan, J. E. (2022). AI: Ethical, social, and security impacts for the present and the future. IT Governance Publishing.
- Mole, A. J. C. (2023). Mastering library and information science. Tobis Press Ltd.
- Nwachukwu, V. N., & Ogwo, U. (2014). Basic principles of information retrieval tools in library and information science. Locco 211 Publishers.
- Ogbonnaya, E. A. (2021). Innovative user-centred library services for twenty-first-century knowledge societies in Nigeria. In V. N. Nwachukwu & U. Ogwo (Eds.), *Essentials of information and communication technologies in libraries: A book of readings* (pp. 192–207). Locco 211 Nigeria Ltd.
- Ogwo, U., Ibegbulem, F., & Nwachukwu, V. N. (2023). Applications and perceived impact of artificial intelligence in academic libraries in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), Article 7907. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7907>
- Prathibha, S. N., & Shilpa, R. N. R. (2021). ChatGPT: A boon to library services. *LIS Links Newsletter*, 7(1). <http://newsletter.links.com>
- Shehu, Y. I., & Dikko, S. (2024). The contribution of artificial intelligence (AI) to the modernization of library systems. Shehu Shagari University of Education, Sokoto: *Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 124–134.
- Soylu, D. (2023). Personalization vs. customization: What's the difference? <https://www.storyly.io/post/personalization-vs-customization-whats-the-difference>
- Udofot, C., & Nwachukwu, V. N. (2019). Utilization of access tools for effective information retrieval in Nigerian university libraries. *Journal of Library Services and Technologies*, 1(1), 48–56.
- Udoh, I. U., Okafor, V. N., & Ekpenyong, G. E. (2020). Strategic information access tools for dissemination of information in academic libraries in a digital era in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), Article 4548. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4548>
- Uhegbu, A. N. (2007). *The information user: Issues and themes*. WHYTEM Publishers.